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Research Article

**FREQUENCY OF POST- PHOTOTHERAPY
THROMBOCYTOPENIA IN HYPERBILIRUBINEMIC
NEONATES**¹Dr. Asif Javeed, ²Dr. Muhammad Anwar, ³Dr. Sadaf Bashir¹Assistant Professor, Department of Pediatric Medicine, Multan Medical and Dental College
/Ibne Sina Hospital Multan²Assistant Professor, Department of Neonatology, Civil Hospital, Bahawalpur³Woman Medical Officer, SJ Maternity Hospital Sahiwal**Article Received:** November 2019 **Accepted:** December 2019 **Published:** January 2020**Abstract:**

Objective: To determine the frequency of post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia in hyperbilirubinemic neonates.
Material and methods: This cross sectional study was conducted at Department of Pediatric Medicine, Multan Medical and Dental College /Ibne Sina Hospital Multan from May 2018 to November 2108 over the period of 6 months. Total 103 neonates apparently healthy, who developed indirect hyperbilirubinaemia and required phototherapy irrespective of gestational age and birth weight. The indication of phototherapy was based on the guidelines of American Academy of Pediatrics 2004. Post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia was assessed.

Results: In present study total 103 neonates were selected. Mean gestational age of neonates was 38.69 ±4.33 weeks and mean birth weight was 2.8 ± 0.6 kg. Out of 103 neonates, post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia was found in 47 (46%) neonates. Post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia was noted in 26 (46.4) male neonates and in 21 (44.7%) female neonates. Insignificant association of gender with post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia was noted with p value 0.8625. Post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia was found in 22 (36.7) neonates of ≥ 37 weeks groups and in 25 (58.1) neonates of < 37 weeks group. Statistically significant association between gestational age and post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia was observed with p value 0.0503.

Conclusion:

Results of this study showed a higher rate of post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia in hyperbilirubinemic neonates. Gender and birth weight of neonate had no effect on development of post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia. But gestational age, type of phototherapy and duration of phototherapy was significantly associated with development of post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia in hyperbilirubinemic neonates.

Keywords: phototherapy, thrombocytopenia, hyperbilirubinemic, neonates

Corresponding author:**Dr. Asif Javeed,**

Assistant Professor,

Department of Pediatric Medicine,

Multan Medical and Dental College /Ibne Sina Hospital Multan

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

The most common pathological condition in the first week of existence is neonatal hyperbilirubinemia (NH). Less than two thirds of babies experience acute yellowing. Physical evidence, such as yellowish skin and sclera discoloration, is induced by the accumulation of bilirubin in newborns. In most infants, unconjugated hyperbilirubinemia shows a normal physiological phenomenon.¹ NH almost affects 60% of term and 80% of first week neonates. Among 3% of average neonates, serum bilirubin above 15 mg levels can be detected. But unchecked, serious hyperbilirubinemia without conjugation is possibly neurotoxic.²

NH is a result of the premature excretative process for bilirubin of the liver. It is also the most common reason for re-entry of newborns in the first week of their existence in the current era of postnatal hospital discharge. Neonatal hyperbilirubinemia concerns both the parents and pediatricians.³⁻⁴

Premature babies have much higher incidence of neonatal jaundice requiring therapeutic intervention than term neonates. Hyperbilirubinemia was found to be the most common morbidity 65% among 137 extremely low birth weight neonates born over a period of 7 years in AIIMS.⁵

High concentrations of unconjugated bilirubin may contribute to bilirubin encephalopathy and ultimately to kernicterus, with catastrophic irreversible neurodevelopment disadvantages.⁶

Therefore, it is of utmost priority to ensure proper treatment of neonatal hyperbilirubinemia. Whether phototherapy or transfusion or pharmacological agent may manage hyperbilirubinemia.⁴ In the prevention and treatment of hyperbilirubinemia, phototherapy plays an important role.⁵ Phototherapy's most seen benefit is that it eliminates the need for transfusion sharing. Phototherapy also has adverse effects as any medication has its side effects. Blood flow amplification and genotoxicity, hyperthermia, food intolerance, lost stools, rashes on the eyes, improvement in the retinal system, dehydration.⁷

The purpose of this study was to find the incidence of thrombocytopenia in neonates with uncomplicated indirect hyperbilirubinemia receiving phototherapy.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross sectional study was conducted at Department of Pediatric Medicine, Multan Medical

and Dental College /Ibne Sina Hospital Multan from May 2018 to November 2108 over the period of 6 months. Total 103 neonates with hyperbilirubinaemia having base line platelet count of more than 150,000/mm³ either male or female were selected. The indication of phototherapy was based on the guidelines of American Academy of Pediatrics 2004.⁸ Neonates with haemolysis, sepsis, anti-platelet drugs given to baby or mother, direct hyperbilirubinaemia, haemangioma and other congenital anomalies were excluded from the study. Neonates who developed features suggestive of sepsis during phototherapy were also excluded. Study was approved by the ethical committee and written informed consent was taken from parents of every baby.

All neonates received phototherapy which provide an intensity of up to 40 μ w when positioned 35 cms from the baby's body. Irradiance was checked by a photo radiometer and was maintained at 30 μ w/nm/cm² at all times. Phototherapy was interrupted only for feeding and nursing for 20 minutes every 2 hours. Platelet count was performed at admission and then at every 24 hours interval as long as phototherapy was given and just after stopping phototherapy.

Thrombocytopenia was defined as platelet count <150,000/mm³. Variables like duration as well as the type of phototherapy and demographic factors such as sex, birth weight, gestational age, and neonatal age were studied.

All the collected was entered in SPSS version 18 and analyzed. Mean and SD was calculated for numerical data like gestational age and weight. Frequencies and percentages were calculated for categorical data like post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia, gender, type of phototherapy. Stratification of age, gender, weight, type of phototherapy and duration of therapy was done. Post stratification chi-square test was applied to detect the detect of these on outcome variable i.e. post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia. P value $\leq$ 0.05 was considered as significant.

RESULTS:

In present study total 103 neonates were selected. Mean gestational age of neonates was 38.69 $\pm$ 4.33 weeks and mean birth weight was 2.8 $\pm$ 0.6 kg. Out of 103 neonates, post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia was found in 47 (46%) neonates. (Fig. 1)

Total 56 (54.37) neonates were male and 47 (45.63%) neonates were female. Post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia was noted in 26 (46.4) male neonates and in 21 (44.7%) female neonates.

Insignificant association of gender with post-phototherapy thrombocytopenia was noted with p value 0.8625. (Table 1)

Gestational age of 60 (61.16) neonates was ≥ 37 weeks and gestational age of 43 (41.75) neonates was < 37 weeks. Post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia was found in 22 (36.7) neonates of ≥ 37 weeks groups and in 25 (58.1) neonates of < 37 weeks group. Statistically significant association between gestational age and post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia was observed with p value 0.0503. (Table 2)

Selected neonates divided in two groups according to weight i.e. ≥ 2500 grams group and <2500 grams group. Weight of 58 (56.31) neonates was ≥ 2500 grams and weight of 45 (43.69) was <2500 grams. Post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia was noted in 27 (46.6) neonates and 24 (53.3) neonates respectively in ≥ 2500 grams group and <2500 grams group. But association of birth weight with post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia was

statistically insignificant with p value 0.6315. (Table 3)

In single Surface Phototherapy (SSPT) groups, there were 75 (72.82) neonates and post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia was noted in 23 (30.7) neonates. In Double Surface Phototherapy (DSPT) group, post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia was found in 24 (85.7) neonates. Association between type of phototherapy and post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia was statistically significant with p value 0.000. (Table 4)

Neonates were divided into 5 groups according to duration of therapy. Total 18 (17.48) neonates belonged to 24 hours group followed by 45 (43.69) neonates to 24-48 hrs group, 21 (20.39) neonates to 48-72 hrs group and 19 (18.45) neonates to >72 hrs group. Post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia was found in 2 (11.1) neonates, 10 (22.2) neonates, 16 (76.2) neonates and 19 (100) neonates respectively. Duration of phototherapy was significantly associated with post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia with p value 0.000. (Table 5)

Fig. 1: Frequency of post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia

Table 1
Association of post-phototherapy thrombocytopenia with gender

Gender	Post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia		Total	P value
	Yes (%)	No (%)		
Male	26 (46.4)	30 (53.6)	56 (54.37)	0.8625
Female	21 (44.7%)	26 (55.3%)	47 (45.63)	
Total	47 (45.63)	56 (54.37)	103	

Table 2: Association of post-phototherapy thrombocytopenia with gestational age

Gestational age	Post-phototherapy thrombocytopenia		Total	P value
	Yes (%)	No (%)		
≥ 37 weeks	22 (36.7)	38 (63.3)	60 (61.16)	0.0503
< 37 weeks	25 (58.1)	18 (41.9)	43 (41.75)	
Total	47 (45.63)	56 (54.37)	103	

Table 3: Association of post-phototherapy thrombocytopenia with birth weight

Birth weight	Post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia		Total	P value
	Yes (%)	No (%)		
≥ 2500 grams	27 (46.6)	31 (53.4)	58 (56.31)	0.6315
<2500 grams	24 (53.3)	21 (46.7)	45 (43.69)	
Total	47 (45.63)	56 (54.37)	103	

Table 4: Association of post-phototherapy thrombocytopenia with type of phototherapy

Type of phototherapy	Post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia		Total	P value
	Yes (%)	No (%)		
SSPT	23 (30.7)	52 (69.3)	75 (72.82)	0.000
DSPT	24 (85.7)	4 (14.3)	28 (27.18)	
Total	47 (45.63)	56 (54.37)	103	

Table 5: Association of post-phototherapy thrombocytopenia with duration of phototherapy

Duration of phototherapy	Post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia		Total	P value
	Yes (%)	No (%)		
24 hrs	2 (11.1)	16 (88.9)	18 (17.48)	000
24-48 hrs	10 (22.2)	35 (77.8)	45 (43.69)	
48-72 hrs	16 (76.2)	5 (23.8)	21 (20.39)	
>72 hrs	19 (100)	0 (0)	19 (18.45)	
Total	47 (45.63)	56 (54.37)	103	

DISCUSSION:

The purpose of present study was to determine the post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia in neonates admitted in our setup. Mean gestational age of neonates was 38.69 ± 4.33 weeks and mean birth weight was 2.8 ± 0.6 kg. Out of 103 neonates, post-phototherapy thrombocytopenia was found in 47 (46%) neonates. In one study by Khera et al,⁹ total 100 hyperbilirubinemic neonates were selected and phototherapy was given to selected neonates. Post-phototherapy thrombocytopenia was found in 35% neonates. Findings of this study in accordance with our findings. Similarly Maurer et al¹⁰ found post-phototherapy thrombocytopenia in 38.7% neonates and Pishwa et al¹¹ found post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia in 49% neonates. All these findings are in agreement with our findings. In our study, total 56 (54.37) neonates were male and 47 (45.63%) neonates were female. Post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia was noted in 26 (46.4) male neonates and in 21 (44.7%) female neonates. Insignificant association of gender with post-phototherapy thrombocytopenia was noted with p value 0.8625. In another study, majority of neonates had mild thrombocytopenia (74%), moderate and severe thrombocytopenia was seen in 23% and 3% cases respectively.¹² In another study conducted 86.4% of neonates had mild thrombocytopenia while moderate and severe thrombocytopenia was seen in 14.6% of babies.¹³

In one study by Bhargava et la,¹⁴ out of 96 neonates included in study 67(69.8 percent) were male and 29(30.2 percent) were female. At the initiation of phototherapy 35 (36.5 percent) neonates were having platelet count above 150000/cumm while after 48 hours of phototherapy 76 (79.2 percent) neonates were having platelet count below 150000/cumm. Majority of neonates had mild (58.2 percent) and moderate (20.8 percent) thrombocytopenia during the first 48 hours of phototherapy. Selected neonates divided in

two groups according to weight i.e. ≥ 2500 grams group and <2500 grams group. Weight of 58 (56.31) neonates was ≥ 2500 grams and weight of 45 (43.69) was <2500 grams. Post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia was noted in 27 (46.6) neonates and 24 (53.3) neonates respectively in ≥ 2500 grams group and <2500 grams group. But association of birth weight with post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia was statistically insignificant with p value 0.6315. In one study higher rate of post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia was found in neonates having weight >2500 grams.¹² The effects of phototherapy on platelet counts in low birth weight neonates and concluded that in 38.7% of babies' platelet count fall below 1, 50,000/ mm³ and the lowest count was 52,000/mm³.¹⁰

In our study, in single Surface Phototherapy (SSPT) groups, there were 75 (72.82) neonates and post-phototherapy thrombocytopenia was noted in 23 (30.7) neonates. In Double Surface Phototherapy (DSPT) group, post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia was found in 24 (85.7) neonates. Association between type of phototherapy and post-phototherapy thrombocytopenia was statistically significant with p value 0.000. Gestational age of 60 (61.16) neonates was ≥ 37 weeks and gestational age of 43 (41.75) neonates was < 37 weeks. Post-phototherapy thrombocytopenia was found in 22 (36.7) neonates of ≥ 37 weeks groups and in 25 (58.1) neonates of < 37 weeks group. Statistically significant association between gestational age and post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia was observed with p value 0.0503. Similarly some other studies showed high rate of Post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia was found in neonates who had received DSPT but the results were not significant.^{9,11}

Neonates were divided into 5 groups according to duration of therapy. Total 18 (17.48) neonates belonged to 24 hours group followed by 45 (43.69)

neonates to 24-48 hrs group, 21 (20.39) neonates to 48-72 hrs group and 19 (18.45) neonates to >72 hrs group. Post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia was found in 2 (11.1) neonates, 10 (22.2) neonates, 16 (76.2) neonates and 19 (100) neonates respectively. Duration of phototherapy was significantly associated with post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia with p value 0.000. The mean platelet counts have increased in neonates who received phototherapy for 48-72 hours which is contrary to our study.⁹ Thrombocytopenia was seen in maximum number of cases during the first 24 hours of phototherapy, and similar findings were noted in a study.^{9,10} That rate of fall of platelet count was more in the first 24 hours of phototherapy which is in contrast to our finding.¹¹ The incidence of thrombocytopenia was observed to be inversely proportional to the age of the neonate at which phototherapy was started. The incidence was significantly more in neonates who received phototherapy on day 2 or 3 of life. This finding was in contrast to the studies; however, their results were not statistically significant.^{9,13,14}

CONCLUSION:

Results of this study showed a higher rate of post-phototherapy thrombocytopenia in hyperbilirubinemic neonates. Gender and birth weight of neonate had no effect on development of post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia. But gestational age, type of phototherapy and duration of phototherapy was significantly associated with development of post- phototherapy thrombocytopenia in hyperbilirubinemic neonates.

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